

What is in Your Knowledge Graph?

Version 1

Description

Data for Latvian Science Council project Izp-2024/1-0665, "What is in Your Knowledge Graph?"

Funder

Latvian Science Council

Grant

Izp-2024/1-0665 What is in your Knowledge Graph?

Researchers

Lelde Lāce (0000-0001-7650-2355), Kārlis Čerāns (0000-0002-0154-5294), Mikus Grasmanis (0000-0002-0668-0970), Uldis Bojārs (0000-0001-7444-565X)

Organizations

Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: What is in Your Knowledge Graph?

Description:

Data for Latvian Science Council project Izp-2024/1-0665, "What is in Your Knowledge Graph?"

Researchers:

Lelde Lāce (0000-0001-7650-2355)

Kārlis Čerāns (0000-0002-0154-5294)

Mikus Grasmanis (0000-0002-0668-0970)

Uldis Bojārs (0000-0001-7444-565X)

Organizations:

Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Latvia

Contact: Čerāns Kārlis (karlis.cerans@lumii.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Science Council

Grants: Izp-2024/1-0665 What is in your Knowledge Graph?

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-04-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Data Schema Collection

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Collect the definitions of data schema structures of Linked Open Data and other data sets to enable data set structure meta-analysis, visual schema presentation and visual query creation over the data sets.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Machine-readable text

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

SQL

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no comprehensive data sets of Linked Open Data schemas of this size available. The existing smaller data sets created earlier by the data set creators would benefit from re-building within a unified process with a traceable data quality assurances.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Linked Data users.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

The decision on the structure of the provided metadata shall be taken during the publication of the data set in the repository (Zenodo). The relevant information about the dataset shall be filled into the dataset submission form.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is typically used for data set publication in Computer Science. It is open for data set publications.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data shall be provided in a form of PostgreSQL A specific interpretation of the data (drawing schema diagrams, creating visual queries) shall be possible using ViziQuer.

ViziQuer Tools

<https://github.com/LUMII-Syslab/viziquer-tools>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data shall be in SQL format and shall be interpretable by PostGreSQL DBMS.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

MIT License

Make the data open

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-04-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kārlis Čerāns (0000-0002-0154-5294)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Other

The data are going to be open for reading

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

